

ICLC 2024 - Proposal for Open Submissions: Video

1. General Information

- **Video Title: Synaptic Soundwaves**
- **Reflective Iterative Scenario Enactments (RISE) / Concordia University Research Lab**
- **Main Contact: Kofi Oduro**
- **Key Contributors: Kofi Oduro (Illestpreacha) & Malte**
- **Duration: 15 minutes**

2. Video Description

“*Synaptic Soundwaves*” is a multisensory plunge that reflects upon the fact that most of the earth is covered by bodies of water, and how these various sources emit sound from their vastly different ecosystems. This is done through sounds produced by hydrophones and vocals while livecoded visuals are displayed on the screen through **LiveCodingYoutube and Hydra**. Where the coded visuals are representing different bodies of water such as but not limited to rivers, tides, hot springs, underwater mountains, coral reefs and the countless fauna that inhabit these environments. Within this performance, we want to reflect upon how these ecosystems are being transformed by both natural and other means that are induced by humans such as pollution, erosion, and climate change. The sheer presence of humans, and the continuous accelerated pace of our hyper-productive and capitalistic framework continue to have great impact and consequences on a lot of natural systems, where ocean ecosystem health tends to be one that we forget about. Our steps, movement, and travels create frequencies that affect life beneath the surface. Our physical bodies emit different chemicals that, depending on the properties of the water, can alter the state and balance of fragile systems.

Also the location of the projector aiming on the floor is meant for the code to be read as if it is speaking as the floor of the Ocean.(Performed for a Human Rights and Arts Conference via **Reflective Iterative Scenario Enactments (RISE)**)

3. Video Link

<https://youtu.be/1371vnV08wY>

4. Biography

Kofi Oduro is an award winning Experiential Storyteller that transforms sounds, images, data, words & code into experiences that nurtures discussion, reflection & interaction. He creates & designs through his decade plus involvement in performance, event and audiovisual production.

His artistic practice is an observation of the world around us that he puts into artworks for others to relate to or disagree with. Through Videography, Poetry, audiovisual and Creative/Live Coding, He tries to highlight the realms of human performance and the human mind in different scenarios.

Malte Leander is a Swedish-French multidisciplinary creator and artist currently residing in Tiohtià:ke/Montreal, Canada. His primary artforms are sound and music, where he often explores soundscape composition, field-recording practices, and voice through text-sound composition and phonetic poetry. He also combines his compositional practice with experimental analog video production and DIY electronic projects in both installation and live performance, where his work often revolves around ecological thematics within sustainable sound practices, acoustic ecology, deep listening, and soundwalking. His creative efforts across disciplines have led him to showcase his work in Canada and internationally, spanning across Scandinavia, Mexico and the United States.